

NEW PHOTO IDENTIFICATION GUIDES

"Biodiversity is one of the most important concepts in contemporary biology, with a broad range of applications"

Twenty-three years ago a group of South African arachnologists decided to initiate the South African National Survey of Arachnida, or SANSA as it is generally known. For the first time, researchers from universities, museums and institutions like the ARC and SANBI worked together on a national biodiversity project, which is focused on documenting the arachnids of South Africa. This national project has several aims:

- to survey and document the arachnid fauna of South Africa
- to describe new species
- to consolidate all the available data on South African arachnids into one relational database
- to make this biodiversity information available to the scientific community
- to address issues concerning their conservation and sustainable use of the local arachnid fauna.

SANSA highlights the importance of a national inventory, the relevance of quality database management, and the significance of capacity development in improving the quality and integration of biodiversity information. This process has strengthened arachnid research in South Africa and enabled the production of a National Species List for South Africa, a major objective of SANSA.

The country now has information for the distribution, lifestyle and conservation status of all known species. There is a renewed interest in spiders, particularly at universities where spider surveys form part of postgraduate research activities. However, the biggest constraint remains the large number of species level determinations required for this kind of survey work. Although spiders are taxonomically better known than most invertebrate taxa, spider systematics is still unstable, even at family level. This is testimony to the vibrance of the field, but makes the production of a hard copy book for the >2000 species impractical. Also, with a large number of undescribed species, such a book would need to be regularly updated to account for the new additions as well.

SANSA will therefore produce a digital series of Photo Identification Guides to make this newly obtained biodiversity information available to scientists and the public. These guides will be available online and eventually published as e-books. Each volume will deal with one family. Large families, such as Araneidae and Thomisidae will consist of more than one volume.

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NEW PHOTO IDENTIFICATION GUIDES—cont.

The guides will be richly illustrated with photographs, maps and line drawings, and a complete reference list.

The following information will be provided:

- Family morphology and lifestyle
- Genus morphology and lifestyle
- Key to genera, where available
- A page for each species, with information on national status, conservation status, global distribution, distribution in South Africa with a map, lifestyle, and taxonomic status.

The guides are being developed and the first drafts of the following families are available:

- AGELLENIDAE (23 pp.)
- AMAUROBIIDAE (26 pp.)
- AMMOXENIDAE (20 pp.)
- ANAPIDAE (12 pp.)
- ANYPHAENIDAE (7 pp.)
- ARANEIDAE PART 1 (70 pp.)
- ARANEIDAE PART 2 (81 pp.)
- ARANEIDAE PART 3 (in prep., about 60 pp.)
- ARCHAEIDAE (20 pp.)
- ATYPIDAE (8 pp.)
- CAPONIIDAE (23 pp.)

HOW TO OBTAIN COPIES

People interested in obtaining a copy can contact me directly at DippenaarA@arc.agric.za. Each of the copies is >11MB. If interested, your name can be placed on a mailing list so that you can be informed as volumes become available. As mentioned, this is a first draft and editorial and other information errors must please be referred back to me. Anyone who has more information or photographs that they would like to add is also welcome to forward it to me. Eventually we will have complete information for each of the species. Volumes will also be made available on a website later.

IMPORTANT NOTE TO ALL THE PHOTOGRAPHERS

We are very grateful to all the photographers who regularly share their images with us. For the Photo Identification Guides we really need your photographs. We would eventually like to have images of most of the species. Photographs of live specimens are really making an important contribution towards identifying spiders, aim the cases where previously only alcohol-preserved material was available.

Unfortunately, we cannot load any more photographs on the ARC Virtual Museum, but SANSa still provides a **Spider Identification Service** for quick identifications by specialists.

See article on page 15 on the web-building behaviour of *Paraplectana walleri*. Morah Cooper sent me a photo of this spider, which eventually resulted in us being able to produce an article dealing with the behaviour of the spider. There are several similar examples of photographers who have made important contributions towards our knowledge of South African spiders. So please - if you see interesting spiders then send us a photo for identification, and maybe you can make a contribution to spider distribution, identification or behaviour.

Photographs can be forwarded to Ansie at DippenaarA@arc.agric.za

NINE NEW *LEPTHERCUS* SPECIES

Lepthercus engelbrechti in vivo. **A** male; **B** female (photos courtesy of Ian Engelbrecht)

Nine new species of trapdoor spiders of the genus *Lepthercus* Purcell, 1902 have been described. Taxonomic work had not been done on this genus for more than 100 years. Redescriptions of *L. dregei* Purcell, 1902 and *L. rattrayi* Hewitt, 1917 were included, along with the female of *L. rattrayi*, which was previously unknown.

This paper includes a phylogenetic analysis based on morphological characters that shows there are two clades. The first clade is the 'Group *haddadi*' that is characterized by males with a curved metatarsus I and a swollen tibia I. The second clade, namely 'Group *dregei*', is characterized by small maxillary cuspules in males. In the paper, the morphological characters are clearly defined to recognize the genus, along with a comprehensive identification key to the species. Distribution maps are also included.

The authors also include notes on the geographic distributions of the two groups in South Africa, showing interesting and important biogeographical zones. 'Group *haddadi*' appears to be more related to the Fynbos Biome of the Western Cape Province, a region that is known for its winter rainfall, and the Indian Ocean Coastal Belt Biome. In contrast, the 'Group *dregei*' is found in the eastern high summer rainfall areas of the country, and largely limited to the Grassland and Savanna Biomes. These species are found in KwaZulu-Natal and the central parts of the Eastern Cape Province. The topography is mainly flat to rolling and is dominated by a single layer of grasses. Exceptions to this divide are the species *L. rattrayi* and *L. dregei*, with *L. rattrayi* occurring within the Albany Thicket Biome, and the type locality for *L. dregei* occurring on the transition between Fynbos and Albany Thicket on the Zuurberg mountains.

The species of the 'Group *haddadi*' are:

- *L. dippenarae* sp. n. (Eastern Cape Province)
- *L. engelbrechti* sp. n. (Eastern and Western Cape Provinces)
- *L. haddadi* sp. n. (Eastern and Western Cape Provinces)
- *L. sofiae* sp. n. (Western Cape Province)
- and *L. rattrayi* Hewitt, 1917 (Eastern Cape Province)

The species from the clade 'Group *dregei*' are:

- *L. confusus* sp. n. (KwaZulu-Natal Province)
- *L. filmeri* sp. n. (Mpumalanga Province)
- *L. kwazuluensis* sp. n. (Free State, KwaZulu-Natal and Eastern Cape Provinces)
- *L. lawrencei* sp. n. (Eastern Cape Province)
- *L. mandelai* sp. n. (Eastern Cape Province)
- and *L. dregei* Purcell, 1902 (Eastern Cape Province)

REFERENCE

RÍOS-TAMAYO, D. & LYLE, R. 2020. The South African genus *Lepthercus* Purcell, 1902 (Araneae: Mygalorphae): phylogeny and taxonomy. *Zootaxa* 4766(2): 261-305. <https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.4766.2.2>

Dr Duniesky Rios-Tamayo

This paper is a collaborative product between the ARC staff member, Robin Lyle, and Dr Duinesky Rios-Tamayo from CONICET – The National Scientific and Technical Research Council in Argentina. He visited the National Collection of Arachnida for the last 6 months of 2018 on a CONICET post-doctoral scholarship. This is the first paper from the research undertaken by Dr Rios-Tamayo during his visit.

THE NEW SALTICIDAE GENUS *MANZUMA*

REFERENCE

AZARKINA, G.N. 2020. *Manzuma* gen. nov., a new aelurilline genus of jumping spiders (Araneae, Salticidae). *European Journal of Taxonomy* 611: 1–47.

In this recently published paper, the new jumping spider genus *Manzuma* was described, four new taxonomic combinations were proposed, and the species were illustrated and redescribed: *M. jocquei*, *M. kenyaensis*, *M. lymph*a and *M. nigritibia*; the male of *M. kenyaensis* and female of *M. lymph*a were described for the first time. Three new species, *M. botswana* from Botswana and South Africa, *M. petroae* from South Africa, and *M. tanzanica* from Tanzania, were described, and the distribution of all *Manzuma* species was mapped. The distribution records of the new species from South Africa are quoted from the article, below:

The two new species for South Africa:

Manzuma botswana Azarkina, 2020

HOLOTYPE: BOTSWANA. ♂ North-West/Ngamiland District, Okavango Delta, Maxwee; 19.4667° S, 23.6500° E; May–Sep. 1976; A. Russell-Smith leg.; floodplain, grassland; MRAC.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Botswana and South Africa

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: 1♂ Limpopo Province, Lekgalameetse Reserve; ca 24.1833° S, 30.1833° E; 25 Sep. 2015; P. & L. Webb leg.; NCA 2019/711.

Manzuma botswana male from Lekgalameetse (photograph courtesy of Peter Webb)

Manzuma petroae Azarkina, 2020

HOLOTYPE: SOUTH AFRICA. ♂ KwaZulu-Natal Province, Ithala Game Reserve, Doornkraal Camp; 27.5122° S, 31.2039° E, 28 Jan. 2014; C. Haddad leg.; hand collecting on ground; NCA 2013/4929.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: Widely distributed, recorded from the following provinces: Eastern Cape, Gauteng, KwaZulu-Natal, Limpopo and North-West.

Manzuma petroae female (photograph courtesy of Vida van der Walt)

NEW FAMILIES

NEW MYGALOMORPHAE FAMILIES

REFERENCE

OPATOVA, V., HAMILTON, C.A., HEDIN, M., MONTES DE OCA, L., KRÁL, J. & BOND, J.E. 2020. Phylogenetic systematics and evolution of the spider infraorder Mygalomorphae using genomic scale data. *Systematic Biology* 69(4): 671-707.

In this study, certain changes to the Mygalomorphae infraorder, using genomic scale data, were made. The affected families, based on past molecular studies using Sanger-sequencing approaches, are the Hexathelidae, Ctenizidae, Cyrtaucheniidae, Dipluridae and Nemesiidae. The changes that affect the mygalomorphs in South Africa include:

FAMILY	GENERA NOW INCLUDED	PREVIOUS FAMILY
ATYPIDAE [NO CHANGE]		
BARYCHELIDAE [NO CHANGE]		
BEMMERIDAE [NEW TO SA]	<i>Homostola</i>	Cyrtaucheniidae
	<i>Spiroctenus</i>	Nemesiidae
CYRTAUCHENIIDAE	<i>Ancylotrypa</i>	
ENTYPESIDAE [NEW TO SA]	<i>Entypesa</i>	Nemesiidae
	<i>Hermacha</i>	Nemesiidae
	<i>Lepthercus</i>	Nemesiidae
EUAGRIDAE [NEW TO SA]	<i>Allothele</i>	Dipluridae
IDIOPIDAE [NO CHANGE]		
ISCHNOTHELIDAE [NEW TO SA]	<i>Thelechoris</i>	Dipluridae
MICROSTIGMATIDAE [NO CHANGE]		
MIGIDAE [NO CHANGE]		
PYCNOTHELIDAE [NEW TO SA]	<i>Pionothele</i>	Nemesiidae
STASIMOPIDAE [NEW TO SA]	<i>Stasimopus</i>	Ctenizidae
THERAPHOSIDAE [NO CHANGE]		

Stasimopus sp. (Stasimopidae)
(photo courtesy of Peter Webb)

Allothele sp. (Euagridae)
(photo courtesy of Peter Webb)

Thelechoris sp. (Ischnothelidae)
(photo courtesy of Peter Webb)

REVISION OF THE AFRICAN PRODIDOMINAE

REFERENCES

RODRIGUES, B.V.B. & RHEIMS, C.A. 2020. An overview of the African genera of Prodidominae spiders: descriptions and remarks (Araneae: Gnaphosidae). *Zootaxa* 4799(1): 1–80.
 RODRIGUES, B.V.B. & RHEIMS, C.A. in press. Phylogenetic analysis of the subfamily Prodidominae (Arachnida: Araneae: Gnaphosidae). *Zoological Journal of the Linnean Society*.

Rodrigues & Rheims (in press) carried out a complete phylogenetic analysis of Prodidominae, using 32 of the 33 valid genera, including representatives of all of the African genera. A taxonomic revision of exclusively African genera of Prodidominae (Gnaphosidae), with the exception of *Prodidomus* and *Theuma*, was completed and twelve genera of Prodidominae were recorded from Africa. From South Africa three genera are known, represented by eight species, of which four are new.

Members of Prodidominae recognized here are small ground-dwelling spiders that are recognized by their eye pattern and clavate body setae.

1. Genus *Austrodomus* Lawrence, 1947

Distribution. Namibia, Mozambique, South Africa and Tanzania.

- *Austrodomus zuluensis* Lawrence, 1947

Distribution. South Africa (KwaZulu-Natal) and Mozambique.

- *Austrodomus scaber* (Purcell, 1904)

Distribution. South Africa and Namibia

Distribution in South Africa: *Western Cape:* Prince Albert. *Limpopo:* Little Leigh (Western Soutpansberg); Vhembe Biosphere Nwanedi Game Reserve; Lajuma Mountain Retreat.

Austrodomus zuluensis female

2. Genus *Eleleis* Simon, 1893

Clavate setae of different sizes on carapace and legs.

- *Eleleis crinita* Simon, 1893

Distribution. South Africa, only known from “Cape Colony” no exact locality.

Carapace after Dalmas (1919)

- *Eleleis haddadi* Rodrigues & Rheims, 2020

Type material. Female holotype from South Africa, Free State, Clocolan, Mpetsane Conservation Estate.

Distribution. South Africa, only known from type locality.

- *Eleleis leleupi* Rodrigues & Rheims, 2020

Type material. Male holotype from South Africa, Cape Province, Clanwilliam, Cederberg.

Distribution. South Africa, only known from type locality.

- *Eleleis limpopo* Rodrigues & Rheims, 2020

Type material. Male holotype from South Africa, Limpopo, Tuinplaas, Springbokvlakte.

Distribution. South Africa and Zambia.

Distribution in South Africa: *Gauteng:* Irene Gem Village Field. *Limpopo:* Little Leigh, Western Soutpansberg.

Eleleis limpopo, a species frequently sampled at Irene (photograph courtesy of Peter Webb).

3. Genus *Purcelliana* Cooke, 1964

Distribution. Namibia and South Africa.

Clavate setae short and similar sized on carapace and legs.

- *Purcelliana problematica* Cooke, 1964

Distribution. South Africa: *Western Cape:* Anysberg Nature Reserve, Prince Albert.

- *Purcelliana cederbergensis* Rodrigues & Rheims, 2020

Type material. Male holotype from South Africa, Western Cape, Cederberg, Wupperthal.

Distribution. South Africa, only known from type locality.

NEW TECHNIQUES

THE 'LAP-SIEVE', A HANDY SPIDER COLLECTING TOOL FOR TRAVELLERS

When travelling to far away countries for collecting purposes, one is often confronted with a trade-off between collecting material and other stuff you will need. In the past I often gave up quite a bit of space and weight for a collecting sieve. The last few years I took a rounded piece of plastic trunk saver screen or olive collecting mesh (!). At the target locality I then bought a plastic basin, cut the bottom out and attached the mesh with a rope.

On our last trip to South Africa I had a rectangular piece (38 x 54 cm) of trunk saver (diamond shaped mesh of 8 mm). I therefore bought a sturdy rectangular plastic box (40 x 28 x 16 cm) (brand ADDIS) with a lid (3.5 cm deep), which I thought would be superfluous. The bottom of the box was cut out and the mesh was attached by gluing the overlapping rims to the sides of the box with duct tape.

The novelty of this sieve is that the lid has two applications: it is used to cover the underside of the sieve during litter collecting and, since it is rebordered, it is ideal as a substrate to sieve upon because one can hold it on one's lap. When you use a fabric sheet, some of the fast animals tend to escape running off the sheet before you can catch them. With the inverted lid, they tend to hide in the groove of the lid margin from where they can easily be caught. It is even possible to lift the lid to have close look at tiny animals. Ideal for the ageing collector!

The complete sieve weighs 680 g and hardly takes any space, as it can be filled with stuff.

Rudy Jocqué & Elisabeth Tybaert

SPIDER PANTRY FROM NELSPRUIT

Allen Jones of the Free State sent us this collection of spiders sampled from a wasp nest in Nelspruit. We can see about 11 different spider species:

- Araneidae 3 spp.
- Oxyopidae 1 sp.
- Cheiracanthiidae 1 sp.
- Philodromidae 2 spp.
- Thomisidae 2 spp.
- Salticidae 2 spp.

CONGRATULATIONS TO RUAN BOOYSEN

Ruan Booysen (photograph courtesy of Norman Larsen)

Well done Ruan!! We hope you can continue with your taxonomic research, as we need taxonomists like you!

Ruan Booysen obtained his MSc degree with distinction. The title of the thesis was "Revision, molecular phylogeny and biology of the spider genus *Micaria* Westring, 1851 (Araneae: Gnaphosidae) in the Afrotropical Region". The objectives of his study were:

- to revise *Micaria* in the Afrotropical Region, providing new and updated records for each of the species,
- evaluating the relationships between them using COI barcoding data,
- and providing information on their biology, mimetic relationships and feeding ecology.

Ruan is an excellent field worker and he sampled extensively for this study. This eventually resulted in the description of 17 new species from the region, of which 12 are new for South Africa. We are looking forward to the first publication.

Ruan was so kind to provide us with information on how to distinguish between *Micaria* and *Castianeira* – two genera that are easily confused.

***MICARIA* (GNAPHOSIDAE) VERSUS *CASTIANEIRA* (CORINNIDAE): A CASE OF MISTAKEN IDENTITY**

Background: There are numerous mimetic relationships that exist in the world of arthropods. One of these relationships is with the pugnacious ant genus *Anoplolepis*, more specifically, *A. custodiens* (Fig. 1). By whom you may ask? Well... several arthropod groups, but the most important here would be, of course, the spiders (Araneae). Thinking about it, three species of spiders come to mind, namely *Micaria beaufortia* (Gnaphosidae), one new species of *Castianeira* (Corinnidae) and *Merenius alberti* (Corinnidae). The two spiders I would like to focus on are *M. beaufortia* and *Castianeira*. Often, from personal observations, these two species co-occur near their mimetic models, with *Castianeira* being the most abundant. My M.Sc. dissertation entailed a revision of the *Micaria* of the Afrotropical region, and as part of it I had to look for *M. beaufortia* among their *Anoplolepis* models. Embarrassing to say, these two spider genera had me confused more than I would like to admit; I mean, at first glance they are almost identical to each other. This begs the question; how would one distinguish these two spiders out in the field? Well, a hand lens is a good start, but you need to know what to look for to maximise your chances of getting the species you need. Here are a few tips that may aid you in distinguishing these spiders from each other:

Eyes: Ruth Hubbard once quoted: "The truth is in the eye of the beholder", and it is very applicable here. Eye morphology is a particularly important character to look at when determining families, genera and even species of spiders...if you have the magnification for it.

By Ruan Booysen

Fig. 1. Habitus of a pugnacious ant, *Anoplolepis custodiens* (photograph courtesy of Ruan Booysen).

These two species belong to two different families and it is evident in the shape and size of their eyes (among other characteristics). *Castianeira* typically have slightly larger eyes than *M. beaufortia*, and more importantly, the posterior median eyes (PME) are round (Fig. 2). In *M. beaufortia* the PME is smaller than the posterior lateral eyes (PLE), but also oblique, a characteristic unique to the gnaphosoid families (Fig. 3).

Micaria (Gnaphosidae) versus *Castianeira* (Corinnidae) - cont.

Fig. 2. *Castianeira* sp. (Corinnidae) (photograph courtesy of Rudolf Steinkampf).

Fig. 3. *Micaria beaufortia* (photograph courtesy of Ruan Booysen).

Colouration and pattern: This may be the easiest way, in my opinion, to distinguish these spiders in the field. These spiders are generally a dark brown or red-brown in colour to help them imitate ants. Both genera have peculiar patterns on their abdomen. Furthermore, their morphology is even adapted to match the ants. Consider *Castianeira* first (Fig. 4): this genus has two to three broad, white, transverse bands across the abdomen and their carapace is partially decorated centrally with white setae. Furthermore, their front femora are much darker than the rest of the leg. *Micaria beaufortia*, on the other hand (Fig. 5), has a single, thin, white transverse line roughly across the middle of the abdomen, with a thin white longitudinal stripe connecting perpendicularly from the transverse line to the spinnerets (may sometimes be dotted). The white setae on the carapace only forms an inverted V towards the posterior margin of the carapace, and the front femora are similar in colour to the rest of the leg.

Size: Depending on the species of *Castianeira* in the area, the adults can be up to 8 mm in length, whereas *Micaria beaufortia* is between 4 and 5 mm in length. This feature is not the best to use, as juvenile *Castianeira* can easily be mistaken for *Micaria beaufortia*.

Fig. 4. *Castianeira* sp. (Corinnidae) (photograph courtesy of Nicolette Josling).

Fig. 5. *Micaria beaufortia* (photograph courtesy of Ruan Booysen).

In conclusion, the next time you see pugnacious ants, look around carefully, things are not always as they seem.

FEEDBACK ON SPIDER SURVEY IN FYNBOS PATCHES IN A FRAGMENTED AGRICULTURAL LANDSCAPE

REFERENCE

THERON, K.J., GAIGHER, R., PRYKE, J.S. & SAMWAYS, M.J. 2020. High quality remnant patches in a complex agricultural landscape sustain high spider diversity. *Biological Conservation* 243: 108480.

This study was carried out in the fynbos biome of the Western Cape Province of South Africa, and which forms part of the Greater Cape Floristic Region, characterized by its Mediterranean climate. A total of 12 remnant patches of natural vegetation were selected within multiple conservancies throughout the fynbos biome. Vacuum sampling and pitfall trapping, that capture plant-dwelling and ground-dwelling spiders, respectively, were used to obtain a good representation of spider species per site. Multiple environmental variables were measured at each site (within patch variables and landscape variables), to determine their influence on spider genus richness and assemblage structure.

A total of 61 genera from 32 families were sampled. The most diverse families were Thomisidae (9 genera), Gnaphosidae (7 genera), Salticidae (6 genera) and Lycosidae (5 genera). However, the most abundant families were Oxyopidae (19.63%), Philodromidae (16.22% of sample), Salticidae (13.66%), Thomisidae (11.38%) and lastly Gnaphosidae (10.67%). A total of seven rare and range-restricted spider species were collected during this study, with a total of 26 individuals. A total of eight species found here have distributions outside Africa. Specifically, *Thomisus daradioides*, *T. citrinellus*, *Euryopis episinoides*, *Pellenes geniculatus*, *Oecobius navus*, *Trachyzelotes jaxartensis*, *Camillina cordifera* and *Dysdera crocata*. All other identified species were endemic to Africa, and most often to South Africa. No invasive spider species were recorded in this study. No spatial autocorrelation was detected (at $p < 0.1$) for any univariate or multivariate response variables. Voucher specimens are housed in the National Collection of Arachnida in Pretoria, where all the identifications were done.

They found that spider diversity is maintained by remnants of good quality natural vegetation, but also influenced by the complexity of the landscape. Preservation of remnant vegetation patches, regardless of size, throughout the privately-owned farm conservancy landscape maintains spider diversity, and so private land conservation should be promoted.

Study area from **STUDENT PROJECT IN FYNBOS**. Also see Theron K.J. 2016. *SANSANews* 25: 9.

RECENT PUBLICATIONS

- ARVIDSSON, F., ADDISON, P., ADDISON, M., HADDAD, C.R. & BIRKHOFER, K. 2020. Weed species, not mulching, affect web-building spider communities and their prey in organic temperate fruit orchards in South Africa. *Ecosphere* 11: e03059.
- AZARKINA, G.N. 2020. *Manzuma* gen. nov., a new aelurilline genus of jumping spiders (Araneae, Salticidae). *European Journal of Taxonomy* 611: 1–47.
- BOTHAM, J.L., HADDAD, C.R., GRYZENHOUT, M., SWART, V.R. & BREDENHAND, E. 2020. State of gene flow shows high genetic diversity of spider species in a montane grassland landscape. *PLoS ONE* 15: e0234437.
- CREWS, S.C., GARCIA, E.L., SPAGNA, J.C., VAN DAM, M.H. & ESPOSITO, L.A. 2020. The life aquatic with spiders (Araneae): repeated evolution of aquatic habitat association in Dictynidae and allied taxa. *Zoological Journal of the Linnean Society* 189: 862–920.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S., HADDAD, C.R. & FOORD, S.H. 2020. First records for the orb-web spider *Arachnura scorpionoides* Vinson, 1863 from South Africa (Araneae: Araneidae). *SANSANews* 34: 12–14.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S., WIESE, L., FOORD, S.H. & HADDAD, C.R. 2020. A list of spider species found in the Addo Elephant National Park, Eastern Cape province, South Africa. *Koedoe* 62(1): a1578.
- MBO, Z. & HADDAD, C. R. 2020. Remarks on two poorly known *Dionycha* spiders from the Afrotropical Region (Araneae: Cheiracanthiidae, Liocranidae). *Arachnology* 18(4): 325–328.
- NENTWIG, W., BLICK, T., GLOOR, D., JÄGER, P. & KROPP, C. 2020. How to deal with destroyed type material? The case of Embrik Strand (Arachnida: Araneae). *Arachnologische Mitteilungen* 59: 22–29.
- NEUMANN, R & SCHNEIDER, J.M. 2020. Males sacrifice their legs to pacify aggressive females in a sexually cannibalistic spider. *Animal Behaviour* 159: 59–67.
- OPATOVA, V., HAMILTON, C.A., HEDIN, M., MONTES DE OCA, L., KRÁL, J. & BOND, J.E. 2020. Phylogenetic systematics and evolution of the spider infraorder Mygalomorphae using genomic scale data. *Systematic Biology* 69(4):671–707.
- PEKÁR, S., PETRÁKOVÁ DUŠÁTKOVÁ, L. & HADDAD, C.R. 2020. No ontogenetic shift in the realised trophic niche but in Batesian mimicry in an ant-eating spider. *Scientific Reports* 10: 1250.
- RÍOS-TAMAYO, D. & LYLE, R. 2020. The South African genus *Lepthercus* Purcell, 1902 (Araneae: Mygalorphae): phylogeny and taxonomy. *Zootaxa* 4766(2): 261–305.
- RODRIGUES, B.V.B. & RHEIMS, C.A. 2020. An overview of the African genera of Prodidominae spiders: descriptions and remarks (Araneae: Gnaphosidae). *Zootaxa* 4799(1): 1–80.
- ŠŤÁHLAVSKÝ, F., FORMAN, M., JUST, P., DENIČ, F., HADDAD, C.R. & OPATOVA, V. 2020. Cytogenetics of entelegyne spiders (Arachnida: Araneae) from southern Africa. *Comparative Cytogenetics* 14: 107–138.
- THERON, K.J., GAIGHER, R., PRYKE, J.S. & SAMWAYS, M.J. 2020. High quality remnant patches in a complex agricultural landscape sustain high spider diversity. *Biological Conservation* 243: 108480.
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OBSERVATIONS ON THE EGG-SACS OF FOUR *PALYSTES* SPP. IN THE FERNKLOOF NATURE RESERVE (ARANEAE: SPARASSIDAE)

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ABSTRACT

The egg-sacs made by four *Palystes* species in the Fernkloof Nature Reserve, Western Cape, South Africa are discussed. In *P. castaneus* Latreille, 1819, *P. leppanae* Pocock, 1902 and *P. superciliosus* L. Koch, 1875, the typical fist-sized sac envelopes of tough, papery silk reinforced with leaves, twigs and other debris were observed. This is the first egg sac report for *P. leppanae*. The females remain in the vicinity of the egg-sac, usually on top of it, until the spiderlings emerge. Of special interest was the egg sac retreat of *P. kreutzmanni* Jäger & Kunz 2010, a fynbos species that deposits the egg sac between the leaves of plants; for the first time the female was found enclosing herself with the eggs in the same retreat.

Key words: SANSa, distribution, Western Cape, Fynbos

INTRODUCTION

As part of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa), biodiversity surveys are undertaken in the Western Cape Province. Fernkloof Nature Reserve (FNR), a fynbos reserve in the Western Cape that covers 1800 ha in the Kleinrivier Mountains above Hermanus, is being surveyed. Six of the seven endemic South African plant families are found in the FNR and it represents an exceptionally high plant diversity, with over 1600 species of the Cape Floral Kingdom being represented.

The aim of this survey is to compile the first checklist of the spider species of the FNR. Surveys in the FNR are still underway and to date 99 genera and 137 spider species have been sampled (Hamilton-Attwell 2018a,b). During the surveys the egg sac retreats made by four *Palystes* species, namely *P. castaneus* Latreille, 1819, *P. leppanae* Pocock, 1902, *P. superciliosus* L. Koch, 1875 and *P. kreutzmanni* Jäger & Kunz, 2010 were observed. Of special interest was the egg sac retreat of *P. kreutzmanni*, an endemic fynbos species.

METHODS

During regular visits in 2018 and 2019 to FNR, four *Palystes* species were recorded and photographed. The plant species that *P. kreutzmanni* was found on were identified and images were taken. Voucher specimens are housed in the National Collection of Arachnida (NCA) at the Agricultural Research Council (ARC) in Pretoria.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fourteen *Palystes* species are known from South Africa (World Spider Catalog 2020). *Palystes* species are nocturnal hunting spiders, and during the day they are inactive and usually found on vegetation. Little is still known about their egg sacs, except for those of *P. castaneus* and *P. superciliosus* (Croeser 1979, 1996; Warren 1926).

Palystes castaneus Latreille, 1819

Palystes castaneus is a southern African endemic species described by Latreille (1819), with the type locality only given as "Cape of Good Hope". The species is presently recorded from Mozambique, Zimbabwe and South Africa. In South Africa it is known from three provinces (Free State, Northern Cape and Western Cape) including several protected areas (Fig. 3).

The egg sac is a fist-sized nest enclosed by tough, papery silk reinforced with leaves, twigs and other debris (Fig. 1). The young *P. superciliosus* hatch some 17 days after the eggs have been laid (Warren 1926) and work their way through the walls of the egg sac about 4 days later (Fig. 2).

Figure 1. *Palystes superciliosus* egg sac.

Figure 2. *Palystes superciliosus* egg sac with emerging spiderlings.

Due to its wide geographical range in southern Africa, the species is listed as Least Concern. This is the first record of the species from FNR. For field identification the uniform dark sternum and ventral abdomen are two of the diagnostic characters of *P. castaneus* (Fig. 4). The egg sac is a fist-sized nest enclosed by tough, papery silk reinforced with leaves, twigs and other debris. It is attached to the vegetation with the female in close proximity (Fig. 5).

Figure 3. Map showing the distribution of *Palystes castaneus* in South Africa.

Figure 4. Female *Palystes castaneus* ventral view (photograph courtesy of Y. Klein).

Figure 5. Female *Palystes castaneus* on egg sac.

***Palystes leppanae* Pocock, 1902**

This is a South African endemic described by Pocock (1902) from Grahamstown. The species is mainly known from the Eastern Provinces, but it is now reported for the first time from FNR in the Western Cape (Fig. 6). Due to its wide geographic range the species is listed as Least Concern.

For field identification the abdomen is mottled greyish-brown with the heart mark outlined; flanked by series of paler spots (Fig. 7); venter with dark crescent mark posterior to epigastric groove followed by rich reddish-brown background decorated with numerous white spots (Fig. 7). The egg sac is large, enclosing the egg cocoon and leaves in a dense silk nest (Fig. 8).

Figure 6. Map showing the distribution of *Palystes leppanae*.

Figure 7. Female *P. leppanae* dorsal view (photograph courtesy of Linda Wiese).

Figure 8. Female *Palystes leppanae* on her egg sac.

***Palystes superciliosus* L. Koch, 1875**

A southern African species described by L. Koch (1875) with the type locality only given as “Südafrika”. It is known from Mozambique, Namibia, Swaziland and South Africa. The species has a very wide distribution throughout South Africa, is known from all the provinces, and occurs in more than 10 protected areas (Fig. 9). Due to its wide geographical range, the species is listed as Least Concern.

Figure 9. Map showing the distribution of *Palystes superciliosus*.

In *P. superciliosus*, males and females have a range of markings, varying from the nearly uniformly pale brown abdomen to specimens of both sexes with an undulating longitudinal dark chocolate line laterally, subtended by a broader white to creamy yellow band. Abdomen ventrally without markings, except for 4 longitudinal striations between spinnerets and dark transverse bar immediately posterior to epigastric groove. Sternum with single dark transverse bar between coxae II. Anterolateral face of coxae dark.

Figure 10. Female *Palystes superciliosus*.

Figure 11. Female *P. superciliosus* on egg sac.

Warren (1926) studied the egg sac of *P. superciliosus* and found they make more than one sac. He estimated that a female laid approximately 800 eggs during an 18-24 month lifespan.

***Palystes kreutzmanni* Jäger & Kunz, 2010**

Palystes kreutzmanni was described by Jäger & Kunz (2010) and is presently known only from four localities in the Western Cape, i.e. Kleinmond, Pringle Bay, Du Toitskloof and FNR (Fig. 12). Due to the species having a small restricted distribution range (<5 000 km²), it is listed as Endangered.

Palystes kreutzmanni differs from other species in the genus by the dark reddish-brown to black sternum, without any bands; the leg coxae are without black bands; ventral abdomen with a red patch between epigastric furrow and spinnerets, becoming blackish anteriorly and posteriorly, including one pair of small white patches in the middle and four longitudinal lines of tiny muscle sigillae; further bright dots situated laterally of the red patch.

The type specimens of *P. kreutzmanni* were sampled in May 2004 from silk retreats made between the apical leaves of a *Leucadendron* sp.

Figure 12. Map showing the distribution of *Palystes kreutzmanni*.

The first specimen of *P. kreutzmanni* from the FNR was sampled during April 2018. It was collected in the top 4-6 leaves of *Othonna quinquedentata* (Asteraceae) (Fig. 15). The female was enclosed in the retreat. When the tip was cut-off (handled), she shot out through the opening of the nest. In the egg-sac retreat several young spiderlings and exoskeletons were present.

Figure 15. (a) *Othonna quinquedentata*, top 4-6 leaves on stem before florescence develops; (b) Opening on top of nest in *O. quinquedentata*; (c) *O. quinquedentata* plant with florescence and flowers.

In June 2019 the second *P. kreutzmanni* was sampled from spindle-shaped nests made in the leaves of *Leucodendron salignum* (tolbosse) (Fig. 16), as also reported by Jäger & Kunz (2010). There were several nests but only two were sampled. On closer inspection, it was found that the one retreat contained a number of small and medium-sized spiderlings, frass and exoskeletons.

Figure 16. (a) *Leucodendron salignum* (female); (b) Male plant; (c) Tips of branches of *L. salignum* with retreats.

Figure 13. Female *P. kreutzmanni*, ventral view.

Figure 14. *Leucadendron* sp. from which *P. kreutzmanni* was sampled.

The second retreat appeared to harbour two objects that turned out to be a female with an egg-sac (Fig. 17). When the nests were opened it became clear that the one nest was older than the other. In the old nest, different sized spiderlings, exoskeletons and frass were observed, as well as remnants of the old egg-sac and possibly eggs that did not hatch, were visible (Fig. 18).

Figure 17. Young retreat between leaves of *Leucodendron salignum*, with egg-sac and female *P. kreutzmanni* protecting the eggs.

Figure 18. Comparison of a young nest and an older egg sac with only dead eggs, some frass and exoskeletons.

What is interesting is that during the process of opening the younger nest, the spider did not move or get agitated (Fig. 17). In the opened nest, the second structure observed during the initial examination was an egg-sac with 46 fresh eggs. No embryos were visible in the eggs yet (Fig. 18).

CONCLUSION

The egg sac and maternal care behaviour of *P. castaneus*, *P. superciliosus* and *P. leppanae* is completely different from *P. kreutzmanni*. In the first three species, the egg sacs are made and then covered with a layer of silk and leaves. This covered large sac is suspended among vegetation. The female usually positioned herself on the egg sac and is aggressive while protecting it. In *P. kreutzmanni*, the female makes the egg sac among the leaves of a plant, then covers it with layers of silk and tightens the surrounding leaves around the retreat with silk. The female stays with the eggs in the retreat.

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NOTE FROM THE EDITOR

Other records of *Palystes* egg sacs are those of *Palystes perornatus* from the Vernon Crookes Nature Reserve, where the female sits on the egg sac.

Palystes perornatus female (photograph courtesy of Dai Herbert).

NOTES ON THE LADYBIRD BEETLE SPIDER *PARAPLECTANA WALLERI* (BLACKWALL, 1865) FROM SABI SANDS GAME RESERVE, SOUTH AFRICA (ARANEAE: ARANEIDAE)

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ABSTRACT

The genus *Paraplectana* Brito Capello, 1867 is known from Africa and Asia. With their bright colours they mimic beetle species belonging to the family Coccinellidae. A *P. walleri* (Blackwall, 1865) female was observed over a three-day period at the Sabi Sands Game Reserve, which lies adjacent to the Kruger National Park, in the Lowveld of Mpumalanga, South Africa. These are the first observations of their web-building and feeding behaviour.

Key words: Cyrtarachninae, behaviour, predation, moths, taxonomy

INTRODUCTION

A yellow ladybird beetle spider was discovered by the first author while working as a field guide at Dulini, a lodge in Sabi Sands Game Reserve that lies adjacent to the Kruger National Park in the Mpumalanga Lowveld, South Africa. The spider was discovered while walking through the bush early one morning. Photographs of the specimen were taken and it was identified as *Paraplectana walleri* (Blackwall, 1865), also known as Waller's Ladybird spider of the family Araneidae (Figs 1, 2).

Members of *Paraplectana* belong to the subfamily Cyrtarachninae, a group of spiders known for their adapted orb-webs. Members of this subfamily construct "spanning thread-webs", a basic orb-web, but the web's diameter, sticky spiral spacing and viscid thread diameter differ from that of typical orb-webs. The viscid threads are studded with large droplets. Each of the short threads between the radii is known as a spanning thread, and is unique in that it breaks when prey comes into contact with it. The prey flies into the web, gets stuck to a viscid thread, the thread breaks, and the spider pulls the prey up to the hub of the web to feed (Stowe 1986; Tanikawa *et al.* 2014). In South Africa, two other species are known to make spanning thread webs, namely *Cyrtarachne ixoides* (Simon, 1870) (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jones 2008) and *Pasilobus dippenaarae* Roff & Haddad, 2015.

Paraplectana walleri is an African endemic described by Blackwall (1865) as *Eurysoma walleri* from Mozambique. The species is known from West, Central and southern Africa, and Madagascar. In South Africa, it is recorded from the Eastern Cape, Mpumalanga and KwaZulu-Natal. With their round, bright yellow bodies decorated with black spots they resemble members of the nightshade ladybird beetle (*Epilachna paykullii*) of the family Coccinellidae (Picker *et al.* 2003). These beetles secrete a fluid from joints in their legs, which gives them a foul taste. This and their bright colours warn would be attackers like birds to ignore them.

STUDY AREA

A *Paraplectana walleri* female was observed in the field at Dulini, a lodge in Sabi Sands Game Reserve. These are the first observations on their web-building behaviour. The area was marked and protected to prevent interference of elephants. The area was observed for three days. The spider was found on a wild mint bush that was situated next to an *Acacia* tree (Fig. 3a-c).

Figure 1. *Paraplectana walleri* female, dorsal view, observed on the bark of an *Acacia* tree.

Figure 2. *Paraplectana walleri* female, ventral view.

RESULTS

Observations started on 6 May 2020 at 18:10. The spider was resting on a Wild Mint bush (*Mentha longifolia* L. (Fig. 3b). At 18:25 the spider started to construct a web by releasing a 3 m length of silk thread. The thread was carried by the wind and it attached to the lower branches of the Wild Mint. At 18:45 another thread attached to dried grass about 42 cm away. At 19:32 the spider moved around the leaves and flowers of the Wild Mint. She parasailed down with a silk thread (Fig. 4), but climbed fast back up again. She deposited silk threads around the vegetation, moving back and forth from the Wild Mint to the grass without using the main strand of the web (Fig. 5). At 19:39 the female was hanging upside down in the web; on 19:45 she added more silk thread in between the main strands. At 19:48 she was again observed hanging upside down in the same spot. The wind was then picking up and on 21:01 a moth landed on the web but the spider moved in the opposite direction and the moth broke free. At 21:05 she checked the web, but at 21:12 she was affected by the strong wind and was only hanging in the middle of the web, swaying from side to side. At 23:16 she was on the main web area but there was no further activity.

On 7 May at 03:00 she was feeding on a moth; she wrapped the moth in silk to form a ball, using her pedipalpi to rotate and chelicerae to crush the moth's body into a smaller size. Nothing was left to waste. She fed while in an upright position. At 04:35 she finished feeding and at 05:52 she started to remove the web by gathering silk threads in her chelicerae (Fig. 6).

Figure 3. (a) Study area at Sabi Sands Game Reserve; (b) Wild Mint bush where spider was found; (c) Arrows indicating areas where the spider was constructing her web.

Figure 6. Female busy removing the old web, gathering silk threads in her chelicerae.

At 06:05 on the 7th of May the female left the main web area climbing down to the Wild Mint bush area and onto grasses. At 07:08 she moved down into the dense vegetation below the mint bush and took up position underneath a mint leaf, where she was not visible from above (Fig. 7).

Figure 7. Female taking up her resting position in a Wild Mint bush during the day.

Figure 4. Female parasailing down on silk thread.

Figure 5. Female *Paraplectana walleri* moving around while building the web.

Late in the afternoon of 7th of May observations started again. At 17:34 the female was located about 32 cm from ground surface, resting. At 17:52 the night activity began. At 17:56 she moved upwards towards the *Acacia nilotica* (dead branches). Abseiling down and using silk threads to climb back up; repeated this action about 1.2 m above ground (Fig. 8). Between 18:08 and 23:03 she was moving between the main web area and mint flower bush laying down and inspecting her web (Fig. 9). In between this she rested for short periods. On 8 May at 03:30 the web was in a different spot as before but there were no sign of any kills. At 05:05 she start removing the web again. At 07:05 she moved to her day time resting area in the mint bush (Fig. 8).

Figure 8. Study area, showing the different areas of activity.

On the 8th of May at 17:54 activity started again. At 18:08 she rapidly started to construct her web, with erratic movements, fast abseiling, and return climbing back again (Fig. 9). From 18:19—21:01 a lot of movement over the main web area was observed, with the spider resting in between. At 21:08 she fell onto the ground on her back while traveling on her existing web down to grass. It took her 48 sec to get back onto her feet. She navigated her way back, although moving slowly. At 21:57 she reached the top of the Mint plant.

Figure 11. Female feeding on the moth.

She then caught a moth (Fig. 10) in the web. She held onto her kill and used her pedipalpi to rotate the prey before consumption began. The feeding finished at 22:32 (Fig. 11).

On 9 May at 05:10 we could not find the spider, with only webbing still visible on the plants. The area was again revisited between 9-11 May, but the spider could not be found.

Figure 9. Female abseiling using silk and her legs.

Figure 10. The moth before it was caught in the web.

CONCLUSION

Little is still known about the behaviour of many spiders in South Africa, especially species of rare genera such as *Paraplectana*. This is our first record of their behaviour in South Africa. We now know that they are active at night, make a spanning-thread web, feed on moths, and they are found in low vegetation and are possible mimics of the nightshade ladybird beetle that is also a low vegetation inhabitant.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

We want to thank The Dulini Collection for allowing the first author observe the specimen.

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FIRST RECORD OF THE ORB-WEB SPIDER *ARANEUS HOLZAPFELAE* LESSERT, 1936 FROM SOUTH AFRICA (ARACHNIDA: ARANEIDAE)

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ABSTRACT

The spotted orb-web spider *Araneus holzapfelae* Lessert, 1936 was described from Mozambique in 1936 and is only known from the type locality. This spider was recorded for the first time from South Africa during the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa). Morphological features of the species were compared with illustrations and literature on the original description of *A. holzapfelae*. This is the first record of the occurrence of *A. holzapfelae* in South Africa, where it was recorded from five provinces. The general morphology of live specimens is discussed, with notes on their behaviour, distribution and conservation status.

Key words: Biodiversity, distribution, South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa)

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Araneus*, represented by 642 species, is large genus with a wide distribution (World Spider Catalog 2020). *Araneus* species in South Africa are still poorly documented, and only 11 endemic species were listed in the first Spider Atlas (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 2010). With the recent publication of Nentwig *et al.* (2020), five of these species are now listed as *nomen dubium*. The only recent paper on a South African *Araneus* included the transfer of *Larinia vara* Kauri, 1950 to *Araneus* (Marusik 2017).

As part of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa), large numbers of specimens were sampled that need to be identified (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 2015). The identification of the araneids, of which most of the genera are not revised, are still a problem. One of the species sampled was identified as the spotted orb-web spider *Araneus holzapfelae* Lessert, 1936. The species is presently known only from the type locality in Mozambique. Morphological features of the species were compared with illustrations and literature on the original description of *A. holzapfelae*. It is presently still only known from the type locality. For the first time, images received for the SANSa Virtual Museum database (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 2012) were available to document the morphology of *A. holzapfelae* in South Africa, with notes on their general behaviour, distribution and conservation status.

METHODS

Voucher specimens are deposited in the National Collection of Arachnida at the Agricultural Research Council, Pretoria (NCA).

TAXONOMIC TREATMENT

Araneus holzapfelae Lessert, 1936

Araneus holzapfeli Lessert, 1936: 246, fig. 40-42.

Description: Size: TL females 4–6 mm, males unknown. *Araneus holzapfeli* is a colourful species and both sexes are recognized by their abdomens decorated with red patterns and four black spots (Figs 1-5). Carapace yellow with eye region dark, with reddish-brown tint extending to the fovea over a slightly elevated area that bears scattered pale long setae (Figs 1, 3); carapace as wide as long, with eye region narrower; eye region with medial area bearing four eyes in two rows, with posterior row slightly procurved; lateral eyes positioned closed together, situated near the carapace edge (Fig. 5); anterior median eyes a little wider apart than the posterior median eyes. Legs similar in colour to carapace, yellow; legs sometimes tinted with green, slender; leg formula 1243; femora and tibiae bearing scattered dark long setae. Abdomen oval, slightly overhanging the carapace; dorsum with white background, decorated with reddish tinted longitudinal bands, merging anteriorly and posteriorly, shape varies between specimens; four black spots present on midline and near posterior end. Epigynum: as in Fig. 6

Behaviour: They are nocturnal orb-web spiders, making their webs at night and resting on vegetation during the day. They are easily sampled with sweep nets and were sampled from the Savanna (Foord *et al.* 2011) and Grassland biomes. Specimens were also sampled from avocado orchards and tomato fields (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 2013).

Figures 1–6. *Araneus holzapfelae*. (1) Female, dorsal view, from Ezemvelo Nature Reserve; (2) Same, lateral view; (3) Female, dorsal view, Empangeni; (4) Female from Richards Bay; (5) Immature female from Drummond; (6) Female epigyne. Photographs courtesy of Peter Webb (1-4) and Andrea Saunders (5).

Distribution: Mozambique. New records: South Africa (Eastern Cape, KwaZulu-Natal and Mpumalanga) (Fig. 7).

Conservation status: The species is protected in the following conserved areas in South Africa: Blouberg Nature Reserve (Muelelwa *et al.* 2010; Foord *et al.* 2019), Ezemvelo Nature Reserve, Faerie Glen Nature Reserve, Kruger National Park, Isandlwane Nature Reserve, Makelali Game Reserve (Whitmore *et al.* 2001) and uMkhuze Game Reserve. Due to its wide distribution range it is listed as Least Concern.

MATERIAL EXAMINED

SOUTH AFRICA. Gauteng: Ezemvelo Nature Reserve (-25.80, 28.77), 1.iii.2014, R. Lyle, 1f, NCA 2014/2552; Pretoria, Faerie Glenn Nature Reserve (-25.74, 28.19), 28.ix.2014, P. Webb, 1m, NCA 2015/3371. **KwaZulu-Natal:** Empangeni (-28.72, 31.88), 25.x.1977, P. Reavell, 1f, NCA 78/135; Richards Bay (-28.78, 32.10) 18.vi.2013, P. Webb, 1f, NCA 2016/1640; iSimangaliso Wetland Park, uMkhuze Game Reserve (-27.63, 32.25), 14.iii. 2013, X. Combrinck, 1m, NCA 2104/3830; uMkhuze Game Reserve (-27.62174, 32.24543), 20.ii. 2010, X. Combrinck, 1m, NCA 2011/2929; Isandlwane Nature Reserve (-28.359, 30.640), 15.iii.2011, M. Stiller, canopy fogging, 1f, NCA 2012/3363; Wakefield Farm, Nottingham Rd. (-29.4987, 29.9106), 24.xi.2015, P. Webb, 1m, NCA 2016/1983.

Limpopo: Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04), 10.iii.2009, V. Gelebe, 1f, NCA 2009/916; Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04), 15.iii.2008, F. Mbedzi, 1f, NCA 2009/917; Little Leigh Farm, Louis Trichardt (-22.949, 29.870), 15.iii.2009, E. Stam, 1m, 1f, NCA 2009/1958, 2009/1957.

Mpumalanga: Brondal (20km NE of Nelspruit) (-25.35, 30.84), 2.xii.1997, M. van den Berg, 1f, NCA 98/249; Kruger National Park, Pretoriuskop, Shabeni (-25.123, 32,237), 10.iii.2012, B. Reynolds, 1f, NCA 2013/2711.

Figure 7. Map showing distribution of *Araneus holzapfelae* in South Africa.

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